

A.

B.

Extended Fig 1.

Extended Fig 2.

Serum iron vs clinical severity

Serum iron saturation vs clinical severity

Serum ferritin vs clinical severity

Serum transferrin vs clinical severity

Extended Data Figure 1. Erythrocyte number and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) are not changed in *Npc1*^{-/-} mice.

Histograms of RBC number (A) and MCHC (B) in *Npc1*^{+/+} mice (open columns) and *Npc1*^{-/-} mice (filled columns) at specified ages. n= 5-7 mice per group

Extended Data Figure 2. Brain iron levels are not significantly changed in *Npc1*^{-/-} mice.

Graph of iron content of *Npc1*^{+/+} brain (filled circles) and *Npc1*^{-/-} brain (filled triangles) at indicated ages. N= 3 per group.

Extended Data Figure 3. Serum iron levels, serum iron saturation, systemic ferritin and serum transferrin levels in NPC1 patients do not correlate with clinical severity. Plots for serum iron (n=105), serum iron saturation (n=104), serum ferritin (n=100) and serum transferrin (n=104) vs clinical severity as determined by annualized severity increment score (ASIS) ²⁴.